

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work At The Imam Ja`afar Alsadiq University

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-----ABSTRACT-----

The current research aims to study if the information and notices provided by the Bologna Path are relevant to student`s work according to the openions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja`afar Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one equestion, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results proved that the information and notices provided by the Bologna Path are relevant to student`s work.

KEYWORDS- Bologna path, Imam Ja`afar Alsadiq University, Technical Colledge, SPSS

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The nature of the problem

What are the point views of the first-stage students of the Department of Communications Technology Engineering at the Technical College at Imam Ja`afar Alsadiq University (pbuh) on the relation of the information and notices provided by the Bologna Path with their work?

1.2 Previous work

There are more alot of previous works about the students` views on Bologna Path , some of them are :

1. Abdaljalil M. Hamad & Rusol A. Mohammed^[1], studied the impact of Bologna Path in giving students the full picture of how they interact with educational contents according to the openions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja`afar Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that Bologna Path giving students the full picture of how they interact with educational contents.
2. Abdaljalil M. Hamad^[2], studied the impact of Bologna Path in using the tools available to help students get the work done effectively according to the openions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja`afar Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the using the tools available in the Bologna Path to help students get the work done effectively .
3. Abdaljalil M. Hamad^[3], studied the impact of Bologna Path in increasing the learning proficiency according to the openionsof students of the Technical College at Imam Ja`afarAlsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of onequestion, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna path increases the students` learning proficiency .

4. Abdaljalil M. Hamad^[4], studied the impact of Bologna Path in strengthening the teacher-student relationship according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (IJSU) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna process increases the strength of teacher-student relationship.
5. Abdaljalil M. Hamad^[5], studied the impact of Bologna Path alongside traditional education without intersecting according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna track can be used alongside traditional education without intersecting..
6. Abdaljalil M. Hamad^[6], studied the impact of Bologna Path in the access of educational content to students despite the weakness of the internet infrastructure according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna path does not prevent the access of educational content to students despite the weakness of the internet infrastructure .
7. Abdaljalil M. Hamad & Rusol A. Mohammed^[7], studied the impact of Bologna Path in the new student's skills required, according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna path requires students to learn new skills .
8. Abdaljalil M. Hamad & Rusol A. Mohammed^[8], studied the impact of Bologna Path in training students to use the computer program dedicated to this ,according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna path requires students training to use the computer program dedicated to this.
9. Abdaljalil M. Hamad & Rusol A. Mohammed^[9], studied the impact of Bologna Path in compatibility of traditional and e-learning ,according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna path requires the compatibility of traditional and e-learning.
10. Abdaljalil M. Hamad & Rusol A. Mohammed^[10], studied the impact of Bologna Path in the implementation of organizational changes according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna path requires changes in the organization..
11. Abdaljalil M. Hamad & Rusol A. Mohammed^[11], studied the impact of Bologna Path as an appropriate system to carry out the student's work effectively according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna path requires changes in the organization..

12. Abdaljalil M.Hamad & Rusol A. Mohammed^[12], studied the impact of Bologna Path in providing the advantage of the information and reports to effectively perform the work according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the application of the Bologna path requires changes in the organization

13. Li, Jiahui^[13], deduces the student-centered concepts, summarizes teachers' practical experiences in promoting students' competency development, and analyzes the role of activities, delivery, assessment, and institutional support, developing a holistic understanding. The findings provide nuanced theoretical insights into the global literature on "how to foster the students with competence during the student-centered course" and offer practical suggestions for realizing the effective student-centered approach in the institutional course.

1.3 Purpose and the contribution

The researcher in the current research aims to identify the consideration of students of the first stage in the Department of Communication Technology Engineering about the implementation of organizational changes according to the opinions of students of the Technical College at Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (Ijsu) - Baghdad - Iraq, the research sample consisted of (109) male and female students from the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and a questionnaire was prepared for that consisted of one question, and the indicators of their validity and stability were verified, then the data were processed statistically using the statistical SPSS computer program, and the results indicated that the information and notices provided by the Bologna Path are relevant to student's work. in university education, as the first experience in Iraq, and this research will contribute to promoting the use of this process or not in the future.

II. THEORITICAL PART

2.1 Bologna Path

Imam Ja'far Alsadiq University (IJSU) is a public university in Iraq that has started implementing the Bologna Track in 2023. On June 19, 1999, educational ministers from 29 different European nations signed an agreement in the Italian city of Bologna that would become known as the Bologna track^[8]. The process seeks to promote a higher education system in Europe that is both internationally competitive and globally appealing.

2.2 Methodology

In this study, a questionnaire was used. It had only one question, it was "Are the information and notices provided by the Bologna Path relevant to student's work!?". This question was taken from some questionnaires ordinary used to test the activities of any university education process.

2.3. Participants of the Study

109 student of both genders (male and female) in communications technical engineering department of technical college at Imam Ja'afar Alsadiq university involved in the study during the academic year 2023- 2024. All the participants were engaged in Bologna path; and consented to respond the question in the study.

2.4 Data Collection and Data Analysis

A survey was used to gather the necessary information. Data were examined using a 5-point Likert scale (I do not agree at all, I do not agree, unaligned, I agree, I completely agree) that was derived from the researcher-created scale.

2.5 SPSS computer Program

The IBM® SPSS® software platform offers advanced statistical analysis, a vast library of machine learning algorithms, text analysis, open-source extensibility, integration with big data and seamless deployment into applications. Its ease of use, flexibility and scalability make SPSS accessible to users of all skill levels. What's more, it's suitable for projects of all sizes and levels of complexity, and can help in finding new opportunities, improve efficiency and minimize risk^[14]

III. PRACTICAL PART

A questionnaire was prepared in the previously mentioned way, and it was distributed to the students of the first stage in the Department of Communications Technology Engineering, and after filling it out by them, it was entered into the SPSS program for statistical analysis, according to the following steps:

1. The SPSS computer program is executed.
2. Clicks File, then New, then Data, then Save, and the results file is named result.pdf

3. Select Variable view and the required information is filled in the name field. Let the name is “Q”.
4. In the label list, the question is written.
5. From the value menu, click on value labels and write the 1st option (1. I do not agree at all). Then click add.
6. Then click on Repeat the process for the rest of the choices (2. I do not agree), (3. Unaligned), (4. I agree) and (5. I completely agree). Then click OK.
7. Click Variable view , and write the selection number of all participants (109).
8. Click on the question, select the question, click on the arrow to transfer the question to the other side, click statistics.
9. Point the options, then continue
10. Click charts , then point the histograms, then show normal curve on histograms, then continue
11. Choose analyze, then descriptive statistics, then explore
12. Choose number, then click on the arrow to transfer the number to the dependent list, then choose the question, then click the 2nd arrow to transfer the question to the factor list, then click statistics, the explore interface will occur.
13. Point all options, then continue
14. Return to explore list, choose plots, another interface will occur , select some options, then continue, then OK.
15. All results will occur.

IV. RESULTS

Table (4-1)

Case Processing Summary

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work		Valid		Missing		Total
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N
number	I do n` t agree at all	6	100.0%	0	0.0%	6
	unaligned	11	100.0%	0	0.0%	11
	I agree	31	100.0%	0	0.0%	31
	I completely agree	61	100.0%	0	0.0%	61

Case Processing Summary

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work		Cases
		Total Percent
number	I do n` t agree at all	100.0%
	unaligned	100.0%
	I agree	100.0%
	I completely agree	100.0%

Table(4-2)

Descriptives

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work		Statistic	Std Error		
number	I do n` t agree at all	Mean	59.8333	4.76576	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		21.8767
			Upper Bound		97.7899
		5% Trimmed Mean	59.8704		
		Median	57.0000		
		Variance	1308.167		
		Std. Deviation	36.16859		
		Minimum	13.00		
		Maximum	106.00		
		Range	93.00		
		Interquartile Range	72.75		
		Skewness	.104		0.845
		Kurtosis	-1.400		1.741
unaligned		Mean	73.6364	6.71264	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		58.6797
			Upper Bound		88.5931

Table (4-3)
Descriptives

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work		Statistic	Std Error
	5% Trimmed Mean	74.2071	
	Median	80.0000	
	Variance	495.655	
	Std. Deviation	22.26330	
	Minimum	35.00	
	Maximum	102.00	
	Range	67.00	
	Interquartile Range	33.00	
	Skewness	-.704	0.661
	Kurtosis	-.568	1.279
I agree	Mean	59.0968	9.56513
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound 47.7313 Upper Bound 70.4623	
	5% Trimmed Mean	59.1953	
	Median	54.0000	
	Variance	960.090	
	Std. Deviation	30.98532	
	Minimum	7.00	
	Maximum	108.00	
	Range	101.00	
	Interquartile Range	58.00	
	Skewness	.053	0.421
	Kurtosis	-1.285	0.821
I completely agree	Mean	49.0492	4.07990
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound 40.8882 Upper Bound 57.2102	
	5% Trimmed Mean	48.4663	
	Median	48.0000	
	Variance	1015.381	
	Std. Deviation	31.86504	
	Minimum	1.00	
	Maximum	109.00	
	Range	108.00	
	Interquartile Range	54.00	
	Skewness	.157	0.306

Table (4-4)
Descriptives

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work	Statistic	Std Error
Kurtosis	-1.170	0.604

Table(4-5)
M-Estimators

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work		Huber's M-Estimator ^a	Tukey's Biweight ^b	Hampel's M-Estimator ^c	Andrews' Waved ^d
number	I do n` t agree at all	59.9030	59.5193	59.8333	59.5148
	unaligned	77.7436	80.1792	77.0349	80.2251
	I agree	58.6441	58.7361	59.1793	58.7333
	I completely agree	47.9126	48.2122	48.3608	48.2162

- a. The weighting constant is 1.339.
- b. The weighting constant is 4.685.
- c. The weighting constants are 1.700, 3.400, and 8.500
- d. The weighting constant is 1.340*pi.

Table (4-6)
Percentiles

		The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work	Percentiles		
			5	10	25
Weighted Average (Definition 1)	number	I do n` t agree at all	13.0000	13.0000	25.7500
		unaligned	35.0000	35.8000	55.0000
		I agree	11.8000	16.2000	31.0000
		I completely agree	3.1000	6.4000	20.5000
Tukey's Hinges	number	I do n` t agree at all			30.0000
		unaligned			61.5000
		I agree			32.5000
		I completely agree			21.0000

**Table (4-7)
Percentiles**

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work			Percentiles			95
			50	75	90	
Weighted Average (Definition 1)	number	I do n't agree at all	57.0000	98.5000	.	105.6000
		unaligned	80.0000	88.0000	101.0000	
		I agree	54.0000	89.0000	102.6000	
		I completely agree	48.0000	74.5000	93.8000	
Tukey's Hinges	number	I do n't agree at all	57.0000	96.0000		103.6000
		unaligned	80.0000	87.5000		
		I agree	54.0000	87.5000		
		I completely agree	48.0000	73.0000		

**Table (4-8)
Extreme Values^a**

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work				Case Number	Value
number	I do n't agree at all	Highest	1	106	106.00
			2	96	96.00
			3	58	58.00
		Lowest	1	13	13.00
			2	30	30.00
			3	56	56.00
	unaligned	Highest	1	102	102.00
			2	97	97.00
			3	88	88.00
			4	87	87.00
			5	84	84.00
		Lowest	1	35	35.00
			2	39	39.00
			3	55	55.00
			4	68	68.00
5			75	75.00	
I agree	Highest	1	108	108.00	
		2	104	104.00	
		3	103	103.00	
		4	101	101.00	
		5	99	99.00	
	Lowest	1	7	7.00	
		2	15	15.00	
		3	16	16.00	
		4	17	17.00	
		5	25	25.00	
I completely agree	Highest	1	109	109.00	
		2	107	107.00	
		3	105	104.00	
		4	100	100.00	
		5	95	95.00	
	Lowest	1	1	1.00	
		2	2	2.00	

Table (4-9)
Extreme Values^a

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work	Value	Case Number
	3	3
	4	4
	5	5

a. The requested number of extreme values exceeds the number of data points. A smaller number of extremes is displayed.

number

Histograms

number
 Figure (4-1)

number
 Figure (4-2)

Figure (4-3)

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

number Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Q19= I do n`t agree at all

Frequency	Stem &	Leaf
2.00	0 .	13
3.00	0 .	559
1.00	1 .	0
Stem width:	100.00	
Each leaf:	1 case(s)	

number Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Q19= unaligned

Frequency	Stem &	Leaf
2.00	0 .	33
8.00	0 .	56788889
1.00	1 .	0
Stem width:	100.00	
Each leaf:	1 case(s)	

number Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Q19= I agree

Frequency	Stem &	Leaf
4.00	0 .	0111
5.00	0 .	22233
7.00	0 .	4444455
6.00	0 .	667777
5.00	0 .	88999
4.00	1 .	0000
Stem width:	100.00	
Each leaf:	1 case(s)	

number Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Q19= I completely agree

Frequency	Stem &	Leaf
14.00	0 .	000000001111111
12.00	0 .	222222233333
10.00	0 .	4444455555
12.00	0 .	666666677777
9.00	0 .	888899999
4.00	1 .	0000

Stem width: 100.00
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Boxplots

The information and notices provided by the Bologna Process are relevant to my work

Figure (4-5)

V. CONCLUSION

The data is categorized into four response levels:

1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis by Level of Agreement

The responses are divided into four categories:

1. I don't agree at all
2. Unaligned
3. I agree
4. I completely agree

1. "I don't agree at all"

- Number of participants: 6
- Mean \approx 59.83
- Standard deviation: 36.17

- Minimum: 13 | Maximum: 106

Comment: The small sample size and high variance indicate considerable disagreement and inconsistency among respondents who strongly disagree. This suggests heterogeneity in this group's attitudes.

2. "Unaligned"

- Number of participants: 11
- Mean ≈ 73.64
- Standard deviation: 22.26
- Range: 35 to 102

Comment: This group shows higher agreement than the previous one with less variability. It likely represents participants with unclear or undecided views toward the Bologna Process.

3. "I agree"

- Number of participants: 31
- Mean ≈ 59.10
- Standard deviation: 30.98
- Values range from 7 to 108

Comment: Despite indicating agreement, the high standard deviation suggests widely varying degrees of agreement, possibly reflecting partial acceptance or conditional support of the Bologna information.

4. "I completely agree"

- Number of participants: 61
- Mean ≈ 49.05
- Standard deviation: 31.87
- Values range from 1 to 109

Comment: Although this group expresses full agreement, their mean score is lower than the "I agree" group. This may indicate a discrepancy between declared agreement and the actual ratings given, perhaps suggesting a tendency to overstate agreement.

2. Visual Analysis (Graphs and Charts)

Histograms

All categories display skewed distributions. In particular, the "I completely agree" group is skewed toward lower values, which may call into question the consistency of their agreement.

Boxplots

The boxplots show significant overlaps between groups, implying that the observed differences may not be statistically significant. This overlap may indicate that perceptions are not clearly delineated by the stated agreement levels and could be influenced by subjective factors.

3. Academic Conclusions

- There is a clear disparity between participants' verbal statements of agreement and their numeric ratings, particularly in the "I completely agree" category.
- The consistently high standard deviations indicate a lack of consensus among participants regarding the usefulness or relevance of Bologna Process information.
- Indicators such as M-estimators and kurtosis values suggest non-normal distributions and the presence of outliers, reinforcing the need for more robust analysis methods.

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